

ML/DL WORKSHOP

In this demonstration, we will consider two projects. Deep Learning project (Image recognition project for MNIST Handwritten Digit Recognition in PyTorch) and a Machine Learning Project (Stock price prediction).

Deep Learning

Deep learning (DL) involves the application of artificial neural networks using modern hardware. DL models possess the ability to discern intricate patterns present in visual imagery, textual content, auditory signals, and various other forms of data to produce accurate insights and predictions. Its success is dependent on large volumes of data.

Three main classes or architectures of deep learning exist. These are multi-layer perceptron (MLP), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), etc. MLP is usually for CSV or spreadsheet files. CNN is usually for image data and RNN for text analysis or sequence prediction.

In this demonstration, a simple CNN would be built, implemented, trained, and used to predict handwritten digits. This is an Image recognition project where a machine is trained to predict handwritten digits.

Dataset: MNIST dataset

Platform: Python/PyTorch/TensorFlow. However for consistency and making our workshop more friendly, we will be using google colab. Tutorials on how to use google colab can be found at <https://www.shiksha.com/online-courses/articles/how-to-use-google-colab-for-machine-learning-projects/>

However, technical details and discussion on how to install and set up the needed softwares and environments for deep learning projects could be given after the workshop.

At the end of the demonstration, the participant should be equipped with the skills to apply what has been learned to other recognized datasets or self-generated datasets to solve real-world problems in their respective fields of expertise.

For more practical purposes, Federated learning could also be explored. This allows a number of participant to come together to train a deep learning model with each participant storing its dataset. A participant however transmits trained parameters (gradients) to a cloud server that does the aggregation of gradients. Participants later downloads the aggregated gradients and use to override its own local gradients.

Deep learning project

MNIST Handwritten Digit Recognition in PyTorch

This is a mini project to build a simple CNN in PyTorch and train it to recognize handwritten digits using the MNIST dataset.

Dataset

The MNIST dataset is made up of 70,000 handwritten images. Out of the 70,000 images, 60,000 are used for training and 10,000 are used for testing. The images are grayscale and have a dimension of 28X28. The images are centred to reduce preprocessing.

The environment to be used is PyTorch. PyTorch is a very popular framework for deep learning like Tensorflow, CNTK and Caffe2. But unlike these other frameworks PyTorch has dynamic execution graphs, meaning the computation graph is created on the fly.

```
#import needed libraries
import torch
import torchvision

#Preparing datasets
n_epochs = 3 #defines how many times we'll loop over the complete training
dataset
batch_size_train = 64
batch_size_test = 1000
learning_rate = 0.01 #hyperparameter for the optimizer
momentum = 0.5 #hyperparameter for the optimizer
log_interval = 10

random_seed = 1
torch.backends.cudnn.enabled = False
torch.manual_seed(random_seed)

# DataLoaders are needed to load the datasets. train_loader is used to
download and transform the the training datasets while the test_loader
downloads and also transforms the test datasets
train_loader = torch.utils.data.DataLoader(
```

```

torchvision.datasets.MNIST('/files/', train=True, download=True,
                           transform=torchvision.transforms.Compose([
                               torchvision.transforms.ToTensor(),
                               torchvision.transforms.Normalize(
                                   (0.1307,), (0.3081,))
                           ])),
batch_size=batch_size_train, shuffle=True)

test_loader = torch.utils.data.DataLoader(
    torchvision.datasets.MNIST('/files/', train=False, download=True,
                               transform=torchvision.transforms.Compose([
                                   torchvision.transforms.ToTensor(),
                                   torchvision.transforms.Normalize(
                                       (0.1307,), (0.3081,))
                               ])),
    batch_size=batch_size_test, shuffle=True)

#Example using the test dataset
examples = enumerate(test_loader)
batch_idx, (example_data, example_targets) = next(examples)

# This codes lets see what one test data batch consists of. This means we
have 1000 examples of 28x28 pixels in grayscale (i.e. no rgb channels,
hence the one)
example_data.shape

# let's plot some of them using matplotlib
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

fig = plt.figure()
for i in range(6):
    plt.subplot(2,3,i+1)
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.imshow(example_data[i][0], cmap='gray', interpolation='none')
    plt.title("Ground Truth: {}".format(example_targets[i]))
    plt.xticks([])
    plt.yticks([])
fig

# Building the Network. In this demonstration, we will use two 2-D
convolutional layers followed by two fully-connected (or linear) layers.
As activation function we'll choose rectified linear units (ReLU in

```

short) and as a means of regularization we'll use two dropout layers. In PyTorch a nice way to build a network is by creating a new class for the network we wish to build

```
import torch.nn as nn
import torch.nn.functional as F
import torch.optim as optim

class Net(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self):
        super(Net, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = nn.Conv2d(1, 10, kernel_size=5)
        self.conv2 = nn.Conv2d(10, 20, kernel_size=5)
        self.conv2_drop = nn.Dropout2d()
        self.fc1 = nn.Linear(320, 50)
        self.fc2 = nn.Linear(50, 10)

    def forward(self, x):
        x = F.relu(F.max_pool2d(self.conv1(x), 2))
        x = F.relu(F.max_pool2d(self.conv2_drop(self.conv2(x)), 2))
        x = x.view(-1, 320)
        x = F.relu(self.fc1(x))
        x = F.dropout(x, training=self.training)
        x = self.fc2(x)
        return F.log_softmax(x)

# initialize the network and the optimizer. If we were using a GPU for
# training, we should have also sent the network parameters to the GPU using
# e.g. network.cuda().
network = Net()
optimizer = optim.SGD(network.parameters(), lr=learning_rate,
                       momentum=momentum)

# Training the Model
train_losses = []
train_counter = []
test_losses = []
test_counter = [i*len(train_loader.dataset) for i in range(n_epochs + 1)]

def train(epoch):
    network.train()
```

```

for batch_idx, (data, target) in enumerate(train_loader):
    optimizer.zero_grad()
    output = network(data)
    loss = F.nll_loss(output, target)
    loss.backward()
    optimizer.step()
    if batch_idx % log_interval == 0:
        print('Train Epoch: {} [{} / {} ( {:.0f}% )] \t Loss: {:.6f}'.format(
            epoch, batch_idx * len(data), len(train_loader.dataset),
            100. * batch_idx / len(train_loader), loss.item()))
        train_losses.append(loss.item())
        train_counter.append(
            (batch_idx*64) + ((epoch-1)*len(train_loader.dataset)))
        #torch.save(network.state_dict(), '/results/model.pth')
        #torch.save(optimizer.state_dict(), '/results/optimizer.pth')

def test():
    network.eval()
    test_loss = 0
    correct = 0
    with torch.no_grad():
        for data, target in test_loader:
            output = network(data)
            test_loss += F.nll_loss(output, target, size_average=False).item()
            pred = output.data.max(1, keepdim=True)[1]
            correct += pred.eq(target.data.view_as(pred)).sum()
    test_loss /= len(test_loader.dataset)
    test_losses.append(test_loss)
    print('\nTest set: Avg. loss: {:.4f}, Accuracy: {} / {} ( {:.0f}% ) \
n'.format(
        test_loss, correct, len(test_loader.dataset),
        100. * correct / len(test_loader.dataset)))

test()
for epoch in range(1, n_epochs + 1):
    train(epoch)
    test()

# Evaluating the Model's Performance
fig = plt.figure()
plt.plot(train_counter, train_losses, color='blue')
plt.scatter(test_counter, test_losses, color='red')

```

```

plt.legend(['Train Loss', 'Test Loss'], loc='upper right')
plt.xlabel('number of training examples seen')
plt.ylabel('negative log likelihood loss')
fig

with torch.no_grad():
    output = network(example_data)

fig = plt.figure()
for i in range(6):
    plt.subplot(2,3,i+1)
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.imshow(example_data[i][0], cmap='gray', interpolation='none')
    plt.title("Prediction: {}".format(
        output.data.max(1, keepdim=True)[1][i].item()))
    plt.xticks([])
    plt.yticks([])
fig

```

Machine Learning Project

Stock price prediction

Dataset can be downloaded from:

<https://www.marketwatch.com/investing/stock/goog/download-data>

The dataset has been provided in the shared folder.

```

# Description: This program predicts the price of G00G stock for a
specific day
# using the Machine Learning algorithm called Support Vector Regression
(SVR)

```

```

#Import the libraries
from sklearn.svm import SVR
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
plt.style.use('seaborn-darkgrid')

```

```
#Load the data
from google.colab import files # Use to load data on Google Colab
uploaded = files.upload() # Use to load data on Google Colab. Dataset is
in the shared folder. Upload to google colab
```

```
# Store and look at the data
df = pd.read_csv('stockdata.csv')
df
```

```
# Get and print last row of data
actual_price = df.tail(1)
actual_price
```

```
# Prepare the data for training
df = df.head(len(df)-1)
df
```

```
# Create an empty list to store the dependent and independent data
days = list()
adj_close_prices = list()
```

```
# Get the date and adjusted close price
df_days = df.loc[:, 'Date']
df_adj_close = df.loc[:, 'adj Close']
```

```
# Create the independent dataset
for day in df_days:
    days.append([int(day.split('/')[1])])
```

```
# Create the dependent dataset
for adj_close_price in df_adj_close:
    adj_close_prices.append(float(adj_close_price))
```

```
# Create 3 Support vector Regression models
```

```
# Create and train a SVR model using a linear kernel
lin_svr = SVR(kernel='linear', C=1000.0 )
```

```

lin_svr.fit(days, adj_close_prices )

# Create and train a SVR model using a polynomial kernel
poly_svr = SVR(kernel='poly', C=1000.0, degree = 2 )
poly_svr.fit(days, adj_close_prices )

# Create and train a SVR model using a rbf kernel
rbf_svr = SVR(kernel='rbf', C=1000.0, gamma = 0.15 )
rbf_svr.fit(days, adj_close_prices )
# Plot the models on a graph to see which has the best fit to the original
data
plt.figure(figsize=(15,7))
plt.scatter(days, adj_close_prices, color='black', label='Original Data')
plt.plot(days, rbf_svr.predict(days), color='green', label='RBF Model')
plt.plot(days, poly_svr.predict(days), color='orange', label='Polynomial
Model')
plt.plot(days, lin_svr.predict(days), color='purple', label='Linear
Model')
plt.legend()
plt.show()

# Show the predicted price for the given day
day = [[30]]

print('The RBF SVR predicted:', rbf_svr.predict(day))
print('The LINEAR SVR predicted:', lin_svr.predict(day))
print('The POLYNOMIAL SVR predicted:', poly_svr.predict(day))

#Print the actual price
print('The actual price:', actual_price['adj Close'][20] )

```

References

<https://machinelearningmastery.com/when-to-use-mlp-cnn-and-rnn-neural-networks/>

Python tutorial

<https://try.codecademy.com/learn-python-3>